

A COMBINED IN VITRO AND IN SILICO PIPELINE FOR THE CHARACTERIZATION OF DRUG-COATED BALLOON COATINGS

Francesca Berti (1), Martina Clerici (1), Ivan Dell'Acqua (1), Elena Bianchi (1), Dimitrios Zantzas (1), Efstathios Stratakos (1), Giancarlo Pennati (1)

1. LaBS, DCMC, Politecnico di Milano, Piazza Leonardo da Vinci 32, 20133 Milano, Italy

Introduction

Drug-coated balloons (DCBs) offer a promising alternative to treat cardiovascular diseases, but face challenges due to limited and poorly understood drug-coating transfer mechanisms [1]. Many factors influence coating transfer effectiveness, among which the contact pressure (CP) exerted by the balloon on the arterial wall during inflation at the target site. This work aims to elucidate the correlation between CP and the transfer and retention of drug coating to the arterial tissue. To achieve this, a comprehensive pipeline is developed for characterizing DCBs, focusing on: i) the amount of coating transferred to the artery during the balloon inflation, and ii) the extent of coating washed off from the arterial wall by the blood flow. In essence, we aim to propose simplified and cost-effective in vitro frameworks, which are designed and supported by computational simulations, to evaluate their performances under controlled conditions.

Methods

A dedicated compression setup, referred to as a *stamping* setup, was developed and 3D printed to simulate the DCB-vessel interaction during inflation at the target site in a reproducible and simplified mechanical process using a tensile testing machine MTS Synergie (100 N load cell) (Fig. 1a). Cylindrical DCB slices were created by resin inflation and cutting of a single commercial device (Pearlflow, L2MTech GmbH) [2], allowing to increase the number of specimens for testing. Swine arterial strips were prepared as counterparts for the *stamping* experiments. CP values were influenced by strip thickness and Young's modulus (denoted as h and E , unknown a priori). To address this, each *stamping* test was articulated in two phases: i) once the strip was mounted on the machine, a first compression test was performed at its lateral ends, allowing to measure h and assess E through a surrogate modeling approach based on the local force-displacement curve; ii) without repositioning the strip, the central portion underwent the effective *stamping* test with the DCB slice, applying a calibrated force to achieve the desired interfacial CP value. This force value was, in turn, identified from another surrogate model taking as input the newly obtained h and E (Fig. 1b). Three different CP values of 20, 50, and 80 KPa were selected for the *stamping* tests. After *stamping*, samples were dried for 24 hours and then inspected by optical microscopy to quantify the coating transferred area by image segmentation. Since drying is a destructive condition applicable once in the specimen's

lifetime, some of the tests at 50 KPa were immediately used for subsequent tests. Indeed, a custom-made millifluidic device was designed to house post-stamping arterial strips, which were then subjected to a 60-second water flow simulating the restored bloodstream at two different flow rates. Two strips were tested per each flow condition and then dried for 24 hours to optically quantify the remaining coated area, assuming as the initial condition the results from the *stamping* tests at the same prescribed CP.

Results

The *stamping* protocol consistently achieved transferred coating areas ranging from 15.6% to 55.4% from 20 to 80 KPa. A linear relationship between the applied CP and the % coating transferred area onto the arterial surface was found regardless of variations in arterial properties (Fig. 1c), demonstrating the effectiveness of the surrogate modeling approach. Such repeatability allowed us to rely on a predictable amount of coating lost during washing-off, which was proportional to the applied flow rate.

Figure 1: Key elements of the in vitro-in silico pipeline

Discussions and Conclusions

By combining in silico and in vitro approaches the proposed pipeline establishes a new standard for DCB coating characterization.

References

1. Marzlin et al, J Interv Cardiol, e5175607, 2022.
2. Stratakos et al. Ann Biomed Eng, 2024

Acknowledgments

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 956470.

